

METHODS OF ORGANIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION LEADERS

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Annotation. *This article discusses the methods of organizing the activities of professional education leaders, the management of vocational education, the distribution of leadership activities and leadership responsibilities in the management of the educational process in the vocational education system.*

Keywords: *professional education, knowledge, management system, management conditions, management art, management methods.*

Introduction. Introduction of new principles of management in the modern education system of the Republic, provision of educational institutions with leaders and teachers capable of performing the tasks assigned to them at a high professional level, organization and improvement of a continuous system of training, retraining and advanced training of leaders and teachers, the legal and regulatory framework for the continuous improvement of the quality and level of professional skills of managers of professional educational institutions has been created and the material and technical base has been expanded. The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan identifies as one of the priorities "the introduction of effective forms and methods of personnel selection, centralized selection of personnel in the civil service, the introduction of a modern system of" identification".

The main part. Governance is an activity inherent in any society, arising from the necessity of life and living. In a market economy, the essence of this activity will be further improved. The main purpose of this is to meet the material and spiritual needs of the working people, and at the same time to develop all social relations. Governance is based on democratic principles in the interests of the people. It is obvious that in the process of such governance, special attention is paid to the human factor, in particular, the interests of the nation and the improvement of national values. After all, for the development of our society, governance must be decisive. Governance is an intrinsic feature of society at any stage of development. This feature is general in nature. Indeed, this feature stems

from the need for people to interact in the work of social society, in the process of life and work, to exchange the products of their material and spiritual activities. Any form of labor - social or collective labor - needs a manager to some extent. The manager coordinates the work of his team. The controller performs general functions arising from the movement of the whole organism, in contrast to the movement of the independent organs of the production organ

An important condition for good governance is the activity of the manager, ie the leader. It is known that society includes economic, socio-political and spiritual spheres. Accordingly, there are three main areas of management. most importantly, economic governance. Because the economy - material production is the basis of life and development of society. National recovery begins with economic restructuring. Economic governance is the most important issue on the agenda. Socio-political governance is the management of relations between different communities of people (social groups, nations, ethnic groups, communities, etc.), as well as relations between people within these communities. The essence of this species is to further strengthen and develop the alliance of different groups. The purpose of this type of governance is to eliminate social disparities, to achieve social cohesion in society, to improve public administration, to transform social self-government. Management of society and the spiritual development of individual members is another key form of governance. In order for the society we live in to develop, it must have a high intellectual quality. Hence the need for scientific management of social education, science and enlightenment, social and cultural services to the population. In the age of the scientific and technological revolution, the management of the sphere of spiritual production is of great importance. This form of management is understood as the management of general education schools, preschool, out-of-school educational institutions, secondary special, vocational education institutions, higher education institutions, faculties and institutes of advanced training and retrainin

Today, the management of vocational education is based on transparency, democracy and self-governance. The supreme body of professional self-government is the pedagogical council, which:

- Defines the main directions of development of professional education, increase and improve the quality of training and education of students and specialists, additional and material base.

- Discussion and selection of different options for the content of education (curricula, programs, textbooks), forms and methods of the educational process, methods of their implementation. discusses and selects.

- Organizes work to improve the creative initiative of engineers and teachers, to improve their pedagogical experience.

- In accordance with the Regulations on the assignment of professional categories approved by the Cabinet of Ministers, teachers attest engineers and teachers, taking into account the views of students and parents, with suggestions.

- Hears and discusses the report of the scientific-pedagogical associations of professional education and the admission commission.

Distribution of leadership activities and leadership responsibilities in the management of the educational process in the vocational education system.

Together with the director of the educational institution, the pedagogical team includes the First Deputy Director for Academic Affairs, Deputy Director for Spiritual and Educational Affairs, Deputy Director for Vocational Education, lead. The art of management is that all leaders of an educational institution should not duplicate each other's activities by directing the team to a common goal, especially each leader should know his role clearly. In the work of the director of the educational institution and his deputies there are interrelated and sometimes common tasks. Therefore, it is very important that these tasks are clearly distributed in specific situations, which prevents duplication in the work process and does not allow any object in the educational institution to be left unattended. For the successful management of the teaching staff, it is important that the director and his deputies allocate the right working time. Planning the following educational process in the management of the pedagogical system Organization of the educational process; control over the educational process; work with department heads and teachers; work with parents and students; organization of methodical work; vocational guidance; Work is carried out in such areas as the analysis of the educational process and the preparation of reports.

The choice of tools to achieve a goal in management activities depends on many factors that affect the final results of the activities of organizations in different ways. Thus, the choice of technical means of automation of management work should be made taking into account technical, economic and organizational factors. If the purpose of the activity is not

clearly selected, there are no criteria to assess whether it has been achieved, it is impossible to measure the effectiveness of the current work of the company, to coordinate the activities of structural units, clear organization is practically impossible. evaluation of the work of the administration and its effectiveness. Due to the vague formulation of goals, it is not possible to rationally distribute responsibilities among management staff and evaluate the performance of each of them. helps motivate.

Goal management is a method of management activity that allows you to anticipate the possible results of activities and plan ways to achieve them

(Figure 1):

Figure 1. Methods of management activities.

Simple goal management is a management method that is developed by the manager without defining the deadlines and the mechanism for achieving the ultimate goal. Simple purposeful management allows entrepreneurial decisions to be made, but does not guarantee that the goal will be achieved. Program management is a management method that develops the purpose and implementation mechanism of management, the time and state of the intermediate values of the process. Normative management is a management method that develops the ultimate goals of managerial management and constraints on parameters and resources. The style of management of the leader by his subordinates in many ways determines the success of the organization, the dynamics of development of the company. Employee motivation, their attitude to work, attitudes, etc. depend on the leadership style

Conclusion. The management of an educational institution in modern conditions is a complex process, the components of which are the correct choice of goals and objectives, the study and in-depth analysis of the achieved level of educational work, a system of rational planning, students and pedagogical teams. organization of activities, selection of optimal methods of raising the level of education and training, effective control.

The solution to these problems depends on the ability of school leaders and teachers to creatively use the latest achievements and best practices in science, team relations, and the active participation of teachers and students in educational work. Goal management is a method of managing and evaluating employees in which: the manager and the subordinate jointly define the main goals of the subordinate; After the allotted time, the manager assesses the level of achievement of goals. The prospects, effectiveness and results of the reforms being carried out in the vocational education system today depend on the interaction between the employer and the educational institution, the integration of the production and training process, the successful introduction of the national qualification system, the perfect professional standard and depends on quality education. The successful introduction of this system will also determine the acceleration of our development in the near future.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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